

Kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of D-fructose by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate in aqueous acetic acid

Ashish Tomar and Arun Kumar*

Department of Chemistry, Meerut College, Meerut-250 001, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : ashishtomar1983@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : In an attempt for developing new oxochromium(VI) reagents for effective and selective oxidation of organic substrates under mild conditions we report in the present paper the kinetic and mechanistic study of the oxidation of D-fructose by tetraethylammonium chlorochromate $(C_2H_5)_4N^+CrO_3Cl^-$. The reaction has been carried out in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v) medium in presence of perchloric acid at constant ionic strength. The reaction has been found to be first-order with respect to each of the oxidant and substrate under pseudo first-order conditions. The reaction is catalysed by acid and follows a first-order dependence on H^+ ion concentration. The ionic strength variation has no effect on the reaction rate. The decrease in dielectric constant of the medium increases the rate of reaction. A 1 : 1 stoichiometry is observed in the oxidation and the reaction rate is not retarded by the addition of radical trapping agent acrylonitrile. Effect of temperature on the rate of oxidation has been studied to show the validity of Arrhenius equation and various activation parameters have been computed. The products of oxidation are identified to be D-erythrose and glycollic acid. On the observed facts a hydride ion transfer mechanism is proposed.

Keywords : Ketohexose, chlorochromate, D-fructose.

Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate¹ adds to the selected list of new Cr^{VI} reagents introduced recently as oxidizing agent for the effective and selective oxidation of organic substrate under mild conditions. In this paper we have reported the kinetics of oxidation of D-fructose with tetraethylammonium chlorochromate.

Experimental

Materials : Tetraethylammonium chlorochromate [TEACC] was prepared by literature method¹. Chromium(VI) oxide (Lancaster) was dissolved in 6 M HCl and was stirred at 0 °C for 5 min. To it a solution of tetraethylammonium hydroxide (20% in H_2O) (Lancaster) was added and the resulting orange yellow solid was washed and dried under reduced pressure. Chromium content was determined iodometrically. Solution of D-fructose was always freshly prepared in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v). The ionic strength was maintained with the use of concentrated solution of $NaClO_4$ (C.D.H.). Perchloric acid (C.D.H.) and all other chemicals were used as such without further purification.

Kinetic measurements : The reaction was carried out under pseudo first-order condition by keeping a large excess of [D-fructose] with respect to [TEACC]. The me-

dium of the reaction was always 1 : 1 (v/v) acetic acid-water in the presence of perchloric acid. Kinetic measurements were made in Shimadzu UV 160 A spectrophotometer at 350 nm. The optical density was measured at various intervals of time. Computation of rate constants was made from the plot of $\log [TEACC]$ against time.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of reaction was performed by conducting the oxidation of D-fructose under the conditions of a known excess of tetraethylammonium chlorochromate. A mixture of D-fructose (0.01 mol dm^{-3}) and TEACC (0.10 mol dm^{-3}) was kept for several hours at 30 °C for the reaction to go to completion. The unconsumed oxidant was estimated iodometrically at the end of the reaction. The stoichiometry was found to be 1 : 1 consistent with the following equation

For product analysis the reaction mixture containing D-fructose and tetraethylammonium chlorochromate in the

Table 1. Rate constant for oxidation of D-fructose by TEACC at 30 °C

[TEACC] × 10 ³ (mol dm ⁻³)	[D-Fructose] × 10 ² (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] × 10 ¹ (mol dm ⁻³)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)	k ₂ × 10 ² (mol ⁻¹ dm ³ s ⁻¹)
0.66	1.66	7.73	5.02	-
0.88	1.66	7.73	5.04	-
1.11	1.66	7.73	5.04	-
1.33	1.66	7.73	5.07	-
1.55	1.66	7.73	5.06	-
1.11	0.33	7.73	1.01	3.07
1.11	0.66	7.73	2.01	3.05
1.11	1.00	7.73	3.06	3.06
1.11	1.33	7.73	4.04	3.04
1.11	1.66	7.73	5.04	3.04
1.11	1.66	3.8	1.69	-
1.11	1.66	5.8	3.24	-
1.11	1.66	7.7	5.04	-
1.11	1.66	9.9	6.76	-
1.11	1.66	11.6	9.12	-

stoichiometric proportion 1 : 1 was left as to equilibrate at 30 °C for 24 h. The reaction mixture was neutralized with NaHCO₃, extracted with chloroform, washed with water and dried over anhydrous MgSO₄. The formation of D-erythrose was confirmed by osazone formation². The presence of glycollic acid was confirmed by spot test.

Results and discussion

The pseudo first-order rate constants were determined at various initial concentrations of reactants. The results obtained are given in Table 1. Plots for different concentrations of tetraethylammonium chlorochromate vs time were linear and the rate constants were independent of initial concentration of tetraethylammonium chlorochromate, showing first-order dependence of the rate on [TEACC]. The reaction is first-order with respect to [D-fructose], too. A plot of log k₁ against log [D-fructose] was linear with a slope of unity thereby confirming first-order dependence in [D-fructose].

Rates of oxidation were found to increase with increase in [H⁺] and the slopes of the plots of log k₁ vs log [HClO₄] were approximately unity showing that the reaction is acid catalyzed and follows the first-order dependence in [HClO₄].

Consequently the empirical rate law is described as follows :

$$-\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} \xrightarrow{\text{[D-Fructose]}} k_{\text{obs}} \frac{[\text{D-Fructose}]}{[\text{TEACC}][\text{HClO}_4]}$$

Effect of ionic concentration : The reaction rate was not influenced by ionic strength when NaClO₄ was initially added to the reaction mixture over the range 0.83 × 10⁻¹ to 5.00 × 10⁻¹ mol dm⁻³ (Table 2).

Effect of radical forming agent : When the reaction was initiated by adding acrylonitrile into a solution containing D-fructose and TEACC, no retardation in the rate was observed. No turbidity due to polymerization of acrylonitrile was observed. Thus, the formation of radical intermediate may be ruled out in the course of the reaction.

Effect of solvent : The reaction has been studied under various compositions of acetic acid-water mixture. It has been observed that the reaction rate increases with the increase of CH₃COOH in acetic acid-water mixture (Fig. 1). A linear plot between log k₁ and 1/D (inverse of dielectric constant) with a positive slope suggests an inter-

Table 2. Effect of varying ionic strength on reaction rate at 30 °C

Sl. no.	NaClO ₄ × 10 ¹ (M)	k ₁ × 10 ⁴ (s ⁻¹)
1.	0.83	5.02
2.	1.66	5.04
3.	2.50	5.04
4.	3.03	5.03
5.	4.16	5.08
6.	5.00	5.07

Note

Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k_1$ versus $1/D$. $[\text{TEACC}] = 1.11 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{D-fructose}] = 1.66 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{HClO}_4] = 7.73 \times 10^{-1} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $[\text{NaClO}_4] = 1.66 \times 10^{-1}$; temp. = 30°C .

action between on ion and a dipole³.

The reaction rates at different temperatures were determined and the values of activation parameters were

calculated from the slope of linear plot of $\log k_1$ vs $1/T$. The data are presented in Table 3. An inspection of data (Table 3) shows that these reactions are characterized by a high negative value of entropy of activation (ΔS^*). This indicates that solvation effect is predominant in the reaction, which suggests the formation of a charged rigid transition state. Furthermore, the high positive value of energy of activation and enthalpy of activation indicate that the intermediate is highly solvated.

In ketohexoses, there are two substituents on the anomeric carbon atom, a hydroxymethyl and a hydroxyl group. Since the hydroxymethyl group has a stronger interaction with axial hydrogen atoms than the hydroxyl group, the anomeric form of ketopyranoses which has an equatorial hydroxymethyl group will be more stable than the other anomer (Scheme 1).

Laser Raman Spectroscopy⁴ reveals that D-fructose exists in equilibrium mixture of pyranoid (59%) and furanoid forms (41%). The main form existing in solution for D-fructose is β -pyranoid⁴.

An increase in the oxidation rate with acidity suggests protonation of TEACC species. The protonated TEACC

Scheme 1

Table 3. Temperature dependence and activation parameters of oxidation of [D-fructose] by [TEACC]

Temp (K)	$K_1 \times 10^4$ (s^{-1})	Temp. coefficient	E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	$\log_{10} A$	ΔH^* (kJ mol^{-1})	ΔG^* (kJ mol^{-1})	$-\Delta S^*$ ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)
293	2.75	-	-	5.13	46.33	91.72	154.92
298	3.71	1.83	44.72	5.12	46.29	92.57	155.30
303	5.04	1.96	51.44	5.11	46.25	93.39	155.58
308	7.28	1.88	50.16	5.13	46.21	94.03	155.27
313	9.52	-	-	5.12	46.17	94.90	155.69
			Mean =				
			48.77				
			(kJ mol^{-1})				

E_a from graph = $48.75 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$.

Scheme 2

interacts with the substrate in the rate determining step. The UV-spectra did not show the existence of intermediate complex formation (Fig. 2) indicating its instability.

There is no evidence of complex formation but the

product formations suggest a mechanism involving intermediate complex formation as shown in Scheme 2. Observation of earlier workers provides support for this mechanism⁵.

Rate law : Based on the proposed mechanism the rate law for the TEACC oxidation of sugar (S) may be derived as

$$\text{Rate} = - \frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} \propto [\text{Ester}]$$

$$\text{or} - \frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = k [\text{Ester}] \quad (5)$$

Fig. 2. UV-spectra of TEACC in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v) (A) and TEACC in aqueous acetic acid 50% (v/v) with D-fructose (B).

Note

From eqs. (1), (2) and 5

$$-\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = kK_1K_2[\text{S}][\text{TEACC}][\text{H}^+]$$

$$-\frac{d[\text{TEACC}]}{dt} = k[\text{S}][\text{TEACC}][\text{H}^+] \quad (6)$$

Conclusion : The oxidation of D-fructose by TEACC in aqueous acetic acid medium proceeds via hydride ion transfer mechanism involving specific cleavage of C₁-C₂ bond of the substance to give the products.

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